

PROBLEMS OF INHABITANTS OF MUKTAGACHA TOWN IN MYMENSINGH DISTRICT IN TERMS OF URBAN SERVICES IMPORTANT FOR SECURITY IN NATURAL DISASTERS

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The term urbanization normally connotes a trend in increasing proportion of the national population living in urban centers (towns & cities), as well as an increase in the number of urban centers over a period of time. Thus, it means population shift from rural to urban areas and the ways in which a society adapts to the change. It generally results in the physical growth of urban areas. It is predicted that by 2050 about 64% of the developing world and 86% of the developed world would be urbanized. An urban area can refer to towns, cities, and suburbs. An urban area includes the city itself, as well as the surrounding areas. Many urban areas are called metropolitan areas. In short, it is a geographical area constituting a city or town, where various urban services like electricity, gas, water supply, health facilities are available. Urban services are necessary transition in provision of facilities provided by urban areas. Generally, it is the responsibility of each country to provide urban facilities to its inhabitants. This study focuses on urban services that people of Muktagachha town in Mymensingh District have enjoyed and the major problems they face while getting urban services, as well. Since Muktagachha town is very close to Mymensingh Sadar the trend of urbanization is increasing here. In fact, it is a well – developed upazila of Mymensingh District. The supply of urban services in this upazillais continuously increasing and the quality of these services tries to increase as stated by the upazilla mayor. However, inhabitants still face various problems in getting urban services. This research is going to discuss what types of problems the inhabitants face and what steps can be taken by the pouro authority to improve the quality of urban services.

Key Words: security, natural disasters, citizens, religiosity level, perception

Introduction

Generally, an urban area is an area where various urban services are available. An urban area is the region surrounding a city. The majority of inhabitants of urban areas have non-agricultural jobs. Urban areas are developed to other subsequent centers, meaning there is the density of human structures such as houses, commercial buildings, roads, bridges, and railways. "Urban area" can refer to towns, cities, and suburbs. An urban area is a location, which is characterized by high human population density and vast human-built features in comparison to the areas surrounding it. Urban services are defined as those public services and public facilities historically and typically provided in cities. Urban services specifically include: electricity facilities, gas facilities, sanitary sewer systems, drainage systems, domestic water systems, street cleaning services, fire and police protection services, public transit services, etc.

It also defines public facilities and public services, which in addition to those defined as urban services, also include streets, roads, highways, sidewalks, street and road lighting systems, traffic signals, parks and recreational facilities, as well as schools, public health, environmental protection and other governmental services. The requirement is that the large majority of population, typically 75%, is engaged in non-agricultural sector. Although some of these services may be provided in rural areas, urban areas are typically served by higher capacity systems capable of providing adequate services at urban densities. Storm and sanitary sewer systems are the only services that are generally exclusive for urban growth areas. Outside urban growth areas storm and sanitary sewer systems are appropriate in limited circumstances, when it is necessary to protect basic public health, safety and the environment and when such services are financially supportable at rural densities and do not permit urban development. Due to the fact that these services are usually necessary to support urban densities, services provided must be adequate in order to allow development at urban densities and to serve development at densities consistent with the land use element. The obligation to provide urban areas with adequate public facilities is not limited to new urban areas. Counties and cities must include in their capital facilities element a plan to provide adequate public facilities to all urban areas, including those existing areas that are developed, but do not currently have a full range of urban governmental services or services necessary to support urban densities. In general, cities are the most appropriate units of government for provision of urban governmental services. However, counties, special purpose districts and private providers also provide urban services, particularly services that are regional in nature. Counties and cities should plan a transformation of governance as urban growth areas develop whereby annexation or incorporation occurs, and non-regional urban services provided by counties are generally transferred to cities.

The capital facilities and transportation element of the county or city comprehensive plan must show how adequately public facilities will be provided and by who. If the county or city with land use authority over an area is not the provider of urban services, a process for maintaining consistency between the land use element and plans for infrastructure provision should be developed consistently with the county wide planning policies. If a city is the designated service provider outside its municipal boundaries, the city capital facilities element must also show how urban services will be provided within their

service area. This should include incorporated areas and any portion of the urban growth area that is assigned as a service area or potential annexation area designated under the capital facilities element.

In general sense, urban problems are those problems that arise in an urban environment from overcrowding and too rapid, uncontrolled development of urban areas. Urban problems are those that result from having a large number of people living, working and travelling within a relatively compact area. They include things such as pollution, sanitation, crime, traffic, housing, unemployment, higher cost of living and higher taxes to pay for city services. In other opinion, urban problems are those which are addressed by urban dwellers. On this earth every urban area has more or less common problems, which include the following: traffic congestion is common in narrow streets; there are poor ventilation and illumination; there are not enough open space and community facilities, e.g. parks, schools; there are improper sanitation facilities (e.g. inadequate kitchen and toilet facilities); there are illegal or unstable structures (e.g. squatter settlements on rooftops); the old buildings are deteriorating; they are overcrowded and have poor living conditions; the buildings have shabby appearance (e.g. peeling paint, rusty window frame); residential flats are mixed with industrial use and they cause noise, air pollution, health and fire hazards. Social problems are common, e.g. crime, vandalism. However, it often differs from city to city, country to country.

Urbanization & urban problems in Bangladesh

According to Rasheed, K.B.S. urbanization is thought to be started in Bangladesh over two thousand years ago, when they were concerned with setting up administration, trade, commerce and certain religious celebrations. It has been related to the background of historical antiquities. The country still does not have the huge urban settlement to be identified as towns and cities in the modern sense of the term. Until recently, the country was largely rural. In 1961, more than 5% of the population lived in urban areas. Since independence in 1971, Bangladesh has experienced enormously high rate of urbanization, which has more than three times exceeded the national population growth rate. Rapid urban settlement is the feature of the contemporary urbanization in Bangladesh. It is estimated that nearly 50% of the national urban population is crammed into four metropolitan cities: Dhaka, Chittagong, Khulna and Rajshahi. All these cities show the increasing number of population in every census. According to the World Bank (WB) Bangladesh Development Series(2007), urbanization in Bangladesh has been going up at higher pace. After independence in 1971, the country's national population growth was 2.2, and the urban population growth was 7% yearly. According to the UN population division, almost 35 million, i.e. 25% of the country's total population lives in urban areas. There are many urban problems in Bangladesh such as urban congestion. Urban congestion is basically overcrowding and an imbalance between the ratio of urban functions and the population also contributed to the problem. The most common urban problems in Bangladesh are: water shortage; mosquito menace; sanitation problems; poor ventilation; poor cleaning and maintenance service; pollution; corruption and insecurity; overcrowding and congested areas; narrow access to roads; lack of parks and playgrounds;

lack of outdoor sports and recreational facilities; lack of health care facilities; fire due to faulty gas and electric line; faulty drainage systems; electricity crisis; drainage congestion; damp houses; in-house water stagnation.

Since Bangladesh is one of the fastest urbanized developing countries, living in urban areas is not much more different experience than it is anywhere else in the world. Due to overgrowing population, small area, poor governance and unstable economy, people of this country face various problems in getting urban services. The problems are more present in most of the district areas in Bangladesh. The people of Dhaka city enjoy most of urban services, but there are problems in getting urban services because Dhaka is the capital of Bangladesh and the most crowded city in Bangladesh. People crowd to Dhaka city in a sense that “*when you need taka go to Dhaka*” because once they come to Dhaka they can get a job to support their family. This causes a great problem in getting urban services. Nowadays, urban service provision authority in Bangladesh faces great problems in providing these services. The urban system in the country is composed of a hierarchy of urban centers by population size from the Mega / Metro City to a small hamlet. Although urban geographers would prefer to classify urban centers in Bangladesh in 7 size classes (Islam & Hossain, 1976), the classification given by the Bangladesh Census Commission is a combination of population size and administrative or governance structure. The Commission has classified the urban centers into following four categories: Megacity, Statistical Metropolitan Areas (SMAs), Pourashavas and Other Urban Areas. It recognized some 522 urban centers in the country in 2001.

– Megacity: A metropolitan city with population of more than 5 million was termed as Megacity in the census of 2001. There is only one Megacity in the country, Dhaka, with an estimated current population of about 14 million. Even in 2001, Dhaka Megacity was not a single city, but an agglomeration of several ones including Dhaka City Corporation area, six Pourashavas and numerous Union Parishads or villages. In 2011, two new City Corporations (Narayanganj and Comilla) have emerged through merger and upgradation of Pourashavas. Such administrative changes require new urban governance system. Dhaka Megacity (or Dhaka Capital Region) will demand a very different governance structure in the future. Governing the megacity region is complex and difficult because of multiplicity of agencies involved in planning and providing different services to the people of the megacity region.

– Statistical Metropolitan Areas (SMAs) are the City Corporations and their adjoining areas with urban characteristics. On the basis of this definition, BBS (2003) identified three Metropolitan areas in the country in 2001, namely Chittagong (3.38 m), Khulna (1.34 m) and Rajshahi (0.7 m), besides Dhaka, which is a Megacity. These three cities had total urban population of 5.42 million, or about 19% of the national urban population in 2001. The Megacity Dhaka and three Metropolitan Cities together absorbed about 56.44% of the total urban population of the country. Metropolitan Cities are given the status of City Corporations. The next category of towns is the Pourashava. The areas declared by the Ministry of Local Government, Rural Development and Co-operatives as Municipal Towns or Pourashavas have the formal urban status with local governments. During the 2001 Census, there were 223 Pourashavas in the country. In the same census, 11 Pourashavas were parts of four largest cities – Dhaka, Chittagong, Khulna and Rajshahi. The remaining pourashavas, 212, had a total population of about 9 million, or 31% of the national urban population. Currently, the number of Pourashavas is about 315.

– Other Urban Areas are upazila headquarters or big market places in rural areas, which have not been declared Pourashava yet during the census operation. The areas, which conform to urban characteristics were considered as Other Urban Areas (OUAs). Recently OUAs, about 200 of them, have absorbed less than 4% of the national urban population. In Bangladesh the urban local governments elect bodies and have their own distinctive governance system and varying degree of autonomy by municipal status (such as Class A, Class B and Class C categories of Pourashavas and the City Corporations).

The following map shows urban centers in Bangladesh with urban hierarchy. It shows data about urban centers in the year of 2001. At present, the numbers of urban centers are increasing more rapidly. The government undertakes various projects and programs, and it also renders various assistance to improve the services and make them available to people.

Map 1.1 – Urban Centers in Bangladesh (2001)
(Source: www.isocarp.net)

Muktagachha upazilla in Mymensingh District is the fastest growing upazilla and the quality of urban services is more or less getting improved. Although people face problems with getting urban services, this study is going to focus on various urban problems and also some recommendations.

Aims & objectives

From the abovementioned problem some aims and objectives of the study have been drawn. These are: to know the existing urban services of Muktagachha town; to identify the present status of urban services; to explore the problems that have been faced by the inhabitants of Muktagachha town; to access the quality of urban services of Muktagachha town; recommendations for betterment.

Literature review

Literature review generally discusses published information in a particular area in a certain time period. It is usually the summary of sources, and it often has an organizational pattern and combines both. When there is time limitation literature review can give an overview or act as a stepping stone. Some literature review related to the research is going to be mentioned here. A.K.M. Helal uz Zaman, Khan Md. Tariqul Alam & Md. Jahirul Islam (2010) in *Urbanization in Bangladesh: Present Status and Policy Implications* stated that a major change to be witnessed in Bangladesh over the next decade would be the rapid spread of urbanization. Unless this spread is effectively managed, the chaotic conditions and accompanying ills like pollution, joblessness and exacerbation of criminal activities are likely to choke growth. An attempt to examine the current situation and trends of urbanization in Bangladesh has been made. Urban migration and population growth trend in Dhaka city has been critically examined. The forces which work behind rapid urbanization in Bangladesh have been identified. An evaluation has also been made to assess the positive and negative impacts of urbanization. Finally, a number of recommendations have been put forward to face the challenges of urbanization in Bangladesh. Rasheed, K.B. Sajjadur (2008) claims that the urban sector in Bangladesh experiences the most severe impact of population growth. Being one of the poorest countries, Bangladesh faces tremendous challenges in coping with infrastructure and service requirement. He mentioned that urban sector dominated non - agricultural activities and it contributes over 60% of GDP as opposed to only 21.77% by agricultural sector. Since independence, the urban population in Bangladesh has grown at an annual average rate of six to seven percent. Consequently, during the four census periods of 1974-2001 urban population of the country has increased six times as compared to 70% increase in rural population. Like most of the emerging economies, urbanization in Bangladesh is a by-product of economic development. He mentioned that from 1974-1981 urban population had grown by over 10%, which is the fastest rate in the country's history. Since then, the country's urban population continued to grow at a rapid rate in response to the push factors (rural poverty and landlessness) obtained in rural areas and the pull factors (better income generating opportunities) of urban centers. The movement of impoverished people from rural to urban areas, especially Dhaka, has contributed to the growth of slum and squatter settlements. Nearly half of the country's total urban population lives in four largest cities – Dhaka, Chittagong, Khulna and Rajshahi in the mentioned order. He also indicated that the decadal growth rate from 1991-2001 for these four cities was 56.5, 44.2, 33.8 and 28.5 percent respectively. Finally, he mentioned that the process of urbanization in Bangladesh is both rapid and uneven, and the ever growing population causes several problems in urbanization process. Rahman, Md. H

(2011) stated that Bangladesh is a developing country with diversified environmental issues, especially in the city area. His study was conducted in Sylhet City Corporation, one of the rapidly developing urban areas in the north-eastern region of Bangladesh, in order to identify the main environmental problems caused by the rapid increase in population, unplanned urbanization and hill cutting. The major environmental problems in the city are traffic obstruction, inappropriate solid waste disposal system, inadequate water supply, water logging state, hill cutting, chance of seismicity, etc. Thus the nature and lifestyle of Sylhet intimately related to hills are under the threat of a drastic imbalance in its ecosystem. This study also investigates the causes of hill cutting along with its probable impact on environment such as deforestation, loss of biodiversity, ecological imbalance and climatic changes, chances of earthquake will increase, destroying natural beauty, causing soil erosion and landslide, etc. Sylhet is located in highly seismic risk zone 3, and most buildings and apartments are constructed without considering earthquake risk. Finally, he recommended that the City Corporation authority should take a new approach to tackle urban problems by investing in new ways to solve them, taking advantages of unused resources and opportunities.

Ahmed, Md.Faysal and Islam, Md. Shahidul (2014) worked on urbanization and environmental problems in Sylhet City and they stated that the process of urbanization in Sylhet City Corporation in Bangladesh (SCC) is unplanned. Their study showed that rapid urbanization had created social, economic, environmental and cultural problems. The effects of urbanization of Sylhet City threaten lives, livelihood, assets, infrastructure, drainage system, slums, environmental quality and economic gains of city dwellers, particularly the urban poorest dwellers. Disposal of garbage in nearby drains low lands, discharge of wastewater into open roadside drains, concentration of hanging latrines in lower income settlements areas, annual flooding, noise and domestication of cattle and poultry are major environmental problems faced by Sylhet City dwellers. Social crime like ransacking, robbery and toll evasion in the city are common to resolve the effect of urbanization, they suggested that the citizens should be conscious as well as government should take proper initiatives and policy.

Ram Ahuja in his book *Social Problems in India* (1997) has examined the cities or towns problems. He says that the increase has led to problems like crime, drug addiction, pollution, juvenile delinquency, begging, alcoholism, corruption, unemployment, housing shortage, overcrowding and slums, poverty, noise, communication and traffic control among others. However, if cities are places of tension and strain, they are also the centre of civilization and culture. They are active, innovative and alive. He identified five major causes of problems in urban life such as migration in and out of a city, industrial growth, apathy of the government, defective town planning and vested interest forces. He also discussed the social effects of urbanization that may be analyzed in relation to family, caste, social status of women and village life. In order to deal with urban problems he has given some suggestions such as systematic development of urban centres and creation of job opportunities, regional planning along with city planning, encouragement to industries to move to backward areas, municipalities to find their own financial resources, encouragement to private transport, adoption of pragmatic housing policy and structural decentralization. In his book the writer has only analyzed the social effects of urbanization. However, he has not discussed environmental, economic, cultural and other effects of urbanization. In Bangladesh urban crime has grown faster than the rural area. Rahman showed that crime related to property such as robbery, dacoity, mugging,

bomb throwing, armed violence and murder were the greatest criminal offences in metropolitan areas in Bangladesh. Moreover, violence against women and drug abuse are also common criminal acts in urban areas.

Islam (1999) identifies some positive and negative impacts of urbanization in Bangladesh due to migration. The positive consequences are higher productivity, greater income opportunity, decline in fertility rate, empowerment, better access to information technology and the negative consequences are housing problem, slums problem, poverty, income inequality, violence and crime, loss of national cultural identity, etc.

Laskar (1996) finds that urbanization rate in Bangladesh has been high in the recent decade. The city grows faster in highly urbanized areas than less urbanized ones and the growth of smaller urban centers is lower than the large urban centers. Rana (2010) showed that although many cities grew faster in Bangladesh, a major challenge to create sustainable cities in Bangladesh arose. The cities face environmental, social and economic problems. Most of the urban areas face the housing problem in developing countries. Most of the people in Dhaka city face the lack of infrastructural services (e.i. water supply and sanitation electricity supply, housing, drainage, roads, gas, etc). Moreover, environmental problems such as air, water and noise pollution are also the major problem in an urban area. Kawsar (2012) showed that Bangladesh had experienced rapid growth of urbanization in the last three decades, but it is a matter of inconvenience that many negative impacts like environmental pollution, unplanned urban growth, income inequality, etc. arise.

Methodology

The study area is large enough to get detailed information. The study has been conducted in Muktagachha town in Mymensingh District. Interviewees have been selected by random sampling. Most of the people from this area get more urban facilities, and they face some problems. Having this in mind, the following steps have been taken to complete the study: primary data have been collected from the field visit, questionnaire, participatory observation and telephonic survey; secondary data have been collected from different organizations and BBS (Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics), books, journals, articles, conference reports and online sources. The collected data were processed and analyzed. Suitable graphs, figures, maps and tables have been prepared. Microsoft Office Excel and GIS (Geographic Information System) software have been used to prepare tables and graphs.

Site selection

The first step of this survey was the selection of the study area. The study area here is Muktagachha town in Mymensingh District. This area has been selected due to several reasons. The area is very close to Mymensingh Sadar. It connects Tangail and Jamalpur Districts with the main area of Mymensingh District. Due to its well-developed highway, this area is well-connected with Mymensingh town. You need about 20-30 minutes to get to the main city of Mymensingh town by vehicle. Since it represents the gateway to Mymensingh from Tangail District, it is important to know about the urban facilities, the quality of them, what problems they face and it is also important to improve the quality of these services for life betterment.

Map 1.2 – Digitized map of study area
(Source: www.muktagachhapouroshova.org)

Map 1.3 – Location of Muktagachha on Google earth map
(Source: www.google earth.com)

Preparation of Questionnaire

The second step of the study was to prepare a questionnaire. A scientific questionnaire based on urban services has been prepared. There were both open - ended and closed - ended questions in the questionnaire.

Data collection and manipulation

Data collection is an inseparable part of any type of research work. The researcher has collected data from the respondents within a semi-structured interview schedule (questionnaire) having both closed and open questionnaire. The survey was conducted in August 2014. After conduct of the survey, researcher manipulated data. After that, the data were processed and analyzed through Microsoft Office Word and Excel (to make essential graphs and tables), Adobe Photoshop, GIS software, Google earth software, and other software programmers' intellectual skills and a wide range of thinking was also applied for analysis purpose.

Data presentation and limitation of the study

After conducting analysis, the researcher has presented the findings in this report by description, graphs, maps, tables, etc. to make this study applicable. There are the following limitations of this research: Time and resources were restricted, so it was not possible to survey all of the area; sometimes people hesitated to give the specific answer; some respondents gave confusing answers; no previous urban services projects have been done; urban service data are not so available. Sometimes pouro authority gave confusing answers like the establishment of postal department and also the establishment of rural electrification board in this upazila.

Conclusion

Bangladesh is one of the world's most densely populated countries. The country is going to witness the rapid spread of urbanization over the next decade. According to the estimation, by 2020 nearly every other man, woman and child will live in an urban area. It is an undeniable fact that urbanization is the inevitable destiny of the human civilization. However, the way cities, both at home and abroad, are growing is not sustainable at all. Therefore, it is an imperative that governments across the globe should fundamentally rethink policies and approach to urbanization management before it is too late.

Study area

Selection of a study area is the most important factor for any analytical research. In this research the study area is Muktagachha town in Mymensingh District. This area has been selected because it is located in the vicinity of the main sadar of Mymensingh Dis-

trict. In recent years the process of urbanization in this area has increased. The most important factor is that this area has great historical background. It has emerged as a great tourist attraction because of the relics of Rajbari (which is currently used as an educational institute). It is also well-known for sweets, which are made here (locally called monda). Muktagachha upazila is also important as a gateway of Tangail and Jamalpur District to the main city of Mymensingh District. In this section the discussion of Muktagachha upazilla will be given.

Geographical location of Muktagachha

Muktagachha Upazila (Mymensingh District) area is 314.71 square kilometers long, located in between 24°36' and 24°52' north latitudes and in between 90°04' and 90°20' east longitudes. It is bounded by Mymensingh Sadar and Jamalpur Sadar upazilas on the north, Fulbaria upazila on the south, Mymensingh Sadar and Fulbaria upazilas on the east, Madhupur and Jamalpur Sadar upazilas on the west.

Map 2.1 – Administrative map of Muktagachha Upazila (Source: www.banglapedia.com)

The following map shows the location of Muktagachha upazila on the map of Bangladesh, as well as on the digitized map of Mymensingh. On the map it can be seen that Muktagachha upazila is very close to Mymensingh Sadar. As a result of well connection, public facilities here are being improved.

Map 2.2 – Location of Muktagachha upazilla in Mymensingh District map

History of Muktagachha

The previous name of Muktagachha was Binodbari. It is believed/fact that the Jomirdars actually came from the Natore or Bogra of our North Bengal. When the first ruler arrived here, a local inhabitant called Muktaram Kormokar welcomed them with a large lamp stand that was made of brass. In that part of our country, people call a lamp stand Gachha. This gratitude pleased the Jamidars and they have renamed the areas Muktagachha using the inhabitant's name and the lamp stand's local name.

History of the War of Liberation in Muktagachha upazila

The freedom fighters resisted the Pak army at Jalchatra on their way to Muktagachha on 23rd April 1971. The freedom fighters under Commander Refazuddin launched attacks on the Pak army at Bat-tali, Bhiti Bari and Muktagachha Police Station. The Pak army conducted brutal mass killing, torture and plundering in the villages of Binodbari, Mankon, Bouerchar Shasha of the upazila. Muktagachha upazilla was liberated on 10th December.

Marks of the War of Liberation are 4 mass killing sites (premises of zamindar Bakul Babu of the upazila sadar, Dumping area, Mankon and Binodbari), 5 mass graves (Dumping area of the upazila sadar, Mazipara of Ishwar Gram, Sreepur in Mankon union, Majhihati, Shasha of Tarati union) and 2 memorial monuments (Majhihati and Bang-banga adjacent Baizana Bridge).

Administrative & Population characteristics of Muktagachha

Muktagacha has 10 Unions/Wards, 261 Mauzas/Mahallas and 283 villages. According to the census of 2001 by BBS, total population here is 366,397 including 185,909 males and 180,488 females; Muslim 348,178, Hindu 17,248, Buddhist 838 and others 133. Indigenous community such as garo belongs to this upazila.

Table 2.1 – Administrative & demographic data of Muktagachha

Upazila								
Municipality	Union	Mouza	Village	Population		Density (per sq km)	Literacy rate (%)	
				Urban	Rural		Urban	Rural
1	10	261	283	37762	328635	1164	48.0	33.8
Municipality								
Area (sq km)	Ward		Mahalla	Population		Density (per sq km)	Literacy rate (%)	
11.97	9		21	37762		3155	48.0	
Union								
Name of union and GO code			Area (acre)	Population		Literacy rate (%)		
				Male	Female			
Kashimpur 51			7489	17618	17068	38.55		
Kumarghata 69			6305	15650	15149	39.16		
Kheruajani 60			7112	16995	16693	33.17		
Ghoga 43			7103	13494	12849	27.73		
Tarati 94			7856	17478	16705	44.30		
Daogaon 25			7579	17079	17249	26.13		
Dulla 34			10284	16401	15747	29.94		
Baragram 16			7290	15405	15245	33.49		
Basati 17			7141	18167	17728	31.03		
Mankon 77			7461	18165	17750	33.62		

(Source: Bangladesh population census 2001, Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics)

Level of Urbanization in Muktagachha Upazila

From the following graph it can be seen that the level of urbanization is the highest in the year of 2011, which is about 12.01%. In 1981, the level of urbanization in this upazilla was about 6.34%. At the present time, the level of urbanization is increasing because of some facilities such as improvement in communication and health facilities, educational facilities, etc. However in the year of 1981 it was only about 6.34%.

Graph 2.1 – Level of urbanization in Muktagacha upazilla
(Source: BBS report, (2001 & 2011))

Increase of urban population in Muktagachha Upazilla

From the following graph it can be seen that the number of urban population in this upazilla is sloping upward. According to the preliminary census of 2011, the number of the total urban population of this upazilla is about 49,915. It was only about 16,292 in the year of 1981. During the period 1991-2001 the decadal growth rate of this upazilla was about 62.36% and the annual growth rate was about 4.97%.

Graph 2.2 – Growth of urban population in Muktagachha upazilla
(Source: BBS report (2001 & 2011))

The following map shows urban population of different upazilas in Mymensingh District. From the map it can be seen that the number of urban population ranges between 49,915 and 61,588. It comes after the highest population number (Mymensingh Sadar – above 350,000). The number of urban population is increasing in the town area of Muktagachha upazilla day by day as public facilities in the town area are much more present than in other areas. Therefore, population density in this area is becoming high and it leads to various urban problems.

Map 2.3 – Urban population in Muktagachha upazila

Urbanization process

Muktagachha paurashava is the only urban area of this upazila. According to the census of 2001, it consists of 9 wards and 21 mahallas, occupying an area of 11.97 square kilometers. The brief description of Muktagachha paurashava is given below. The Muktagachha paurashava was established in the year of 1875. The Muktagachha town committee was replaced by the paurashava after the promulgation of the Bangladesh local council and municipal committee (amendment) order in 1972. Muktagachha paurashava is one of the oldest paurashavas of Mymensingh District. It covers an area of 11.97 square kilometres, having a population of 49,915 according to the preliminary census report of 2011. There are about 20 educational institutions, 428 mosques, 28 temples, 3 churches, 4 cinema halls, 1 library, 3 playgrounds, 5 dak bungalows and 1 post office in this paurashava. This paurashava falls under the category of “B” class.

Table 2.2 – Changing pattern of Muktagacha Paurashava

Events	1981	1991	2001	2011
Population (both sexes)	1,629,2	2,043,4	3,776	4,991,5
Male	8,574	1,078,7	1,945,7	-
Female	7,718	9,650	1,830,5	-
Literacy rate (7+ year)	-	46.3%	48.0%	-

(Source: BBS report, (2001 & 2011))

Industries

There are 15 biscuit factories, 12 oil mills, 3 presses, 16 saw mills, 221 rice mills, 2 bidi factories and 12 dairy products (ghee) factories in this upazila.

Main sources of income

Although agriculture is the main occupation here, at present non-agricultural sectors are increasing. The percentage of these sectors is the following: agriculture – 59.26%, non-agriculture – 4.61%, industry – 1.13%, commerce – 11.29%, transport and communication – 6.32%, service – 4.96%, construction – 1.35%, religious service – 0.22%, rent and remittance – 0.28% and others – 10.58%.

Cultural activities

Muktagacha has always been the place to nourish various cultural activities. The Zamindars of Muktagacha were always conscious of cultural activities. Raja Jagat Kishore Acharya Choudhury was the true patron of culture. He brought famous cultural people like Ustad Allauddin Khan, Hafiz Ali Khan, Dabir Khan and many others to Muktagachha. A lot of people directly nourish the field of culture. People here practice Rabin-dra Sangeet, Nazrul Sangeet, Kirtan, Lalon Geeti, etc. In addition, various cultural activities are held all year round.

Religious activities & religious institutions

Muktagachha has a long tradition of being the peaceful land decorated with religious harmony. Both the Hindus and Muslims are of brotherly nature and live peacefully together. Eid is celebrated with a lot of grandeur. On this day, not only the Muslims do visit each other's home, but the Hindus visit Muslims, as well. People share many food items made at home. Many fairs locally called Mela are organized. "Durgapuja" is the main religious function of the Hindu community here. During "Durgapuja" the whole town takes a festive look. People of all communities enjoy "Durgapuja". Devotees go from one Man-

dap to other to visit the Pratima of Goddess Durga. Besides this, all other religious activities are peacefully observed. There is a 200 year old twin Shiva temple just outside Rajbari, where Durgapuja is celebrated. There are many religious institutions here since different religious groups of people live here. People of different religions live peacefully and cooperate with each other. The table on the following shows information of religious institutions.

Table 2.3 – Number of religious institutions

ID	Description	Number/amount enumerated by pouro authority	Number/amount from banglapedia
1	Eidgah field	07	--
2	Mosque	580	521
3	Mandir	16	22
4	Church	--	5
5	Cemetery	04	5
6	Crematorium	02	--

(Source: www.muktagachapourashava.org and www.banglapedia.org)

An overview of urban services in Muktagachha town

As it is already known, urban services are those that are provided by the government to the people within its jurisdiction, either directly (through the public sector) or by financing provision of services. The term is associated with a social consensus that certain services should be available to all, regardless of income. Generally, services that are provided by the government in urban areas are more or less available. However, since Bangladesh is a developing country and the most populous country in the world, the government of this country faces problems in providing services to its inhabitants. We know that people move to urban areas for various reasons, but among all of the reasons urban pull factor and rural push factor are important. People come more to Muktagachha town because of the availability of urban services, so the rate of people migrating here is increasing. In this section an overview of urban services and their present condition will be discussed.

List of urban services

Urban service areas are those areas in and around the existing communities, which are most suitable for urban development and capable of providing a full range of urban services. The urban service area boundaries represent the outer limits of planned urban growth over a long-term planning period. The people of Muktagachha town have enjoyed some urban service facilities. A list of these facilities is given below: electricity supply, water supply, waste management, drainage & sewerage facilities, health facilities, recreational facilities, transportation & communication facilities, infrastructural facilities (road, bridge or culvert, lamp post), market and shop facilities, facilities in slum areas, Internet service, telecommunications, etc.

Present scenario of urban services

The development of urban services in Muktagachha town depends on economic development of the main center of Mymensingh District (sadar). This town has not seen the expected development as there is no development program in Mymensingh main town since the independence of Bangladesh in 1971. The construction of garment industries, multi-storey and commercial buildings is still limited in number here. Rickshaw is the main mode of transportation within this area and growth of the number of cars is sluggish. Modern shopping malls and well-furnished residential hotels are also less in number. However, at present there are more development programs here and also the supply of urban services is increasing in the main city of Mymensingh Sadar. Urban services in Muktagachha town are also increasing as spider net from the core. Since this area is so close to the main sadar area, people are willing to stay here and work as commuters from Muktagachha town to the main area of Mymensingh District. Therefore, urban facilities here are being improved. The present situation of urban services is discussed in the following section.

Electricity supply

Electricity is the most important part of modern civilization. It is significant for socio-economic development, as well as for modern life. It is one of those discoveries that have changed the daily life of everybody on the planet. It is the key component to modern technology and without it most of the things that we use every day simply could not work and would never be created. Indeed, modern society would be incredibly different. Imagine how different things would be today without the Internet. The World Wide Web (WWW) has had a huge effect on our lives. It has made everybody more aware of the world they live in, and it has allowed them to learn about our surroundings and know more about how near enough everything within modern society works. It is our gateway to knowledge, and it allows us to find out nearly anything within a matter of seconds, hence electricity has made us an incredibly intelligent and aware society. There is no power generation station in Muktagachha town. Here electricity comes from the national grid. For the purpose of socio-economic development of the inhabitants of Muktagachha town and to have happy life Mymensingh Rural Electrification Committee-1 started its activities, as well as services in 1984. Until June 2014 it has spread its territory to 512 kilometres (approximately), which covers 1,710,922 receivers and creates opportunities to 1,600,570 people. It also helps in agricultural development, industrial development and employment opportunities to most of the rural people in this area. According to Banglapedia "All the wards and unions of the upazilla are under rural electrification network. However, 21.49% of the dwelling households have access to electricity." According to the director of the Committee, "Rural Electrification Committee cannot generate electricity for its own needs. It can rather get electricity supply from the national power grid. With the earnest efforts of the Government, load shedding in this area is very little in amount. Sometimes faulty in the electricity line & for repairing supply of electricity kept stop. We are extremely sorry for this short-term disturbance and hope that the recipient has to be patient and should cooperate with us." "Mymensingh Rural Electrification

Committee buys electricity at immediate price from PDB and then distributes it to the recipients. Therefore, electricity bill is the main source of income of this Committee. If the electricity bill is not paid the Committee faces problems. Also, the number of cases of stealing electric wires and transformers has recently increased. Therefore, the recipients and also the Committee face serious problems. Thus, we request our receivers to cooperate with us in order to stop stealing”, he also said.

Water supply

Water is the vital element in life. With two thirds of the earth's surface covered by water and the human body consisting of 75 percent of it, it is obvious that water is one of the prime elements responsible for life on the earth. Water circulates through the land just as it does through the human body, transporting, dissolving and replenishing nutrients and organic matter while carrying away waste material. Further in the body, it regulates the activities of fluids, tissues, cells, lymph, blood and glandular secretions. Water supply in this upazila by water supply authority is a recent phenomenon. Most of the inhabitants, who live here, said that they have personal motor for water supply to their house. Some people do not have personal motor and they use supply water from the authority or personal tube well. Most of the people who use supply water said that it fulfilled their water demand. They do not face water scarcity. However, if some bad situation occurs (load shedding for a long time) then people have to face many problems because they cannot get much water. In their annual survey report in 2012 the pouro authority showed that it had established productive tube well (normal pump, submersible pump) and manual tube well in various areas of this upazila from time to time to meet water demand of the inhabitants. The following table shows statistics on water supply system in this area.

Table 3.2 – Statistics on Water supply (pipeline 19.491 km)

ID	Productive tube well					Manual tube well
	Type	Size	Year of establishment	Depth (meter)	Productive capacity (m3/hour)	
1	Normal pump (KSB)	6 ft	1995	580	571.48	394
2	Normal pump (KSB)	6 ft	1996	560	571.48	
3	Submersible	3 ft	2011	350	350.00	

(Source: Information desk, Muktagachha pouroshova, 2014)

The pouro authority said that if anyone would like to get connection of supply water whether it is residential or commercial, first they have to apply to the mayor of the pouroshova in a prescribed form. They have to mention what type of diameter line they want. They have to pay fee for the first time connection. The amount of fee depends on the distance from the user to the source of water or reservoir. The following table shows statistics on water supply in this upazilla. It shows that there is 1 high reservoir here. This reservoir is located in Moddhohishsha area. From this reservoir water is supplied to all recipients

(residential & commercial). The table also shows daily demand for water, duration of water supply, amount of daily water supply, leakage and repair of line from 2009-2012, total population under water supply, water supply coverage and other important data.

Table 3.4 – Information about water supply system until 2012

ID	Description	Units	Number/amount/condition	
1	High reservoir	Number	01	
2	Water supply	Hour	7 hours	
3	Daily demand for water	Cubic meter	4976.40	
4	Daily water supply	Cubic meter	1492.96	
5	Leakage repair in previous years	2009	Number	13
		2010	Number	10
		2011	Number	12
		2012	Number	07
6	Total street high drain in pouro area	Number	22	
7	Total population under water supply	Number	4737	
8	Water coverage	%	30%	
9	Presence of arsenic in water	Yes/no	0.004 mg/l	
10	Presence of iron in water	Yes	1.08 mg/l	
11	Water metering system	Yes/no	No	

(Source: Information desk, Muktagachha pouroushova, 2014)

Health facilities and sanitation system

Health and sanitation facilities are very important to lead healthy and secure life. In Muktagachha the authority tries to improve the quality of health care services. There is one upazilla health care center here. According to Banglapedia report, the number of health care centers is described in the following table.

Table 3.5 – Number of health care centers in Muktagachha

ID	Description	Number
1	Upazilla health complex	1
2	Satellite clinic	4
3	Hospital	1
4	Community clinic	27
5	Family planning center	6
6	Veterinary hospital	1

(Source: www.en.banglapedia.org)

The table on the following shows the existing health facilities enumerated by the upazila health complex. This table shows that there is 1 upazila health complex with 31 beds, 4 union sub centers with no bed, 6 union health and family welfare centers and also data on other health facilities. This table also shows that the number of private and community clinics is great here, too. Furthermore, some of the owners of these private hospitals claim that the facilities of private clinics are increasing to a great extent.

Table 3.6 – *The existing health facilities enumerated by the upazilla health complex (modified)*

ID	Facility type	Total No.	No. of Beds
1	Number of upazilla health complex	1	31
2	Number of Union Sub-centers	4	0
3	Number of union health & family welfare centers	6	0
4	Number of rural/urban/Thana dispensaries	0	0
5	Number of community clinics	39	0
6	Number of trauma centers	0	0
7	Number of chest disease clinics (TB clinics)	0	0
8	Number of NGO clinics/facilities	0	0
9	Number of MCWCs	0	0

Source: app.dghs.gov.bd

The following graph shows the child health that is enumerated by the upazilla health complex. The graph shows that children under 5 years of age are more vulnerable to death calculated as 436. In order to enumerate child health, the upazilla health complex authority took into consideration the data on children from January-December 2013. The total birth rate here at this time is 9063, whereas the percent of fully vaccinated children is 96%.

The following table represents maternal health, which came to this health complex in January-December 2013. It shows that during the mentioned time period the total number of all ANC recipients was 9030, the total number of deliveries here was 9104, whereas the total number of maternal death was 18 and TT coverage 26%. Generally, the poor people of rural Muktagachha seem to come here and use health services. Rich people prefer to go to Mymensingh Sadar and get better health facilities.

Table 3.7 – *Maternal Health January-December 2013 enumerated by Upazilla health complex (modified)*

ID	Description	Number
1	All ANC recipients	9030
2	Total number of deliveries	9104
3	Number of maternal death	18
4	Valid TT coverage	26.00%

(Source: app.dghs.gov.bd)

According to the statistical report of Muktagachha Upazilla on health services, it has been seen that there is one upazilla health complex and its present condition is good. Private clinics have also been established in a large number in this area. Thus, it can be seen that the overall health facilities in this upazilla are not bad and the pouro authority, as well as the private sectors, are trying to improve health facilities here.

Table 3.8 – *Number of health care centers counted by pouroshova*

ID	Description	Number/amount	Present condition
1	Number of EPI centers	--	--
2	Hospital guided by pourashava	01	Good
3	Clinic guided by pourashava	--	--
4	Number of govt. hospital	01	Good
5	Private clinic	12	--

Sanitation is equally important as health facilities. If there is a good sanitation system then people will lead life free from diseases. However, being a developing country, our sanitation system is not good. Most of the people in rural Bangladesh areas do not have proper sanitation system. There is an attempt to improve sanitation facilities. For this purpose they have constructed public toilets in different places in this area. The following table shows statistics on sanitation and types of toilets in this area. The statistics was conducted by the pouro authority in 2012.

Table 3.9 – Sanitation facilities enumerated by the pouro authority

ID	Description	Number/amount	Situation
1	Public toilet	07	Good
2	Community toilet	20	Good
3	Septic tank & toilet with septic tank	1870	Good
4	Open toilet	1607	

(Source: Information desk, Muktagachha pouroshova, 2014)

According to Banglapedia report on Muktagachha, it says that 27.16% (rural – 24.28% and urban – 53.93%) of dwelling households of the upazilla use sanitary latrines, 37.37% (rural – 38.52% and urban – 26.70%) of dwelling households use non-sanitary latrines whereas 35.46% of households do not have latrine facilities.

Waste disposal & management system

According to Wikipedia, “Waste management is the generation, prevention, characterization, monitoring, treatment, handling, reuse and residual disposition of solid wastes”. There are various types of solid waste including municipal (residential, institutional, commercial), agricultural and special (health care, household hazardous wastes, sewage sludge). The term usually relates to materials produced by human activity, and the process is generally undertaken to reduce their effects on health, the environment or aesthetics.

According to the pouro authority of Muktagachha town, they are working hard to minimize waste and they are also trying hard to maintain the secure environment. For this purpose they engage the huge number of cleaners to collect waste from dustbins in various areas and dispose them to the waste disposal ground. However, the authority said that there was no recycling process presented here. They only dispose garbage here after collecting it from dustbins constructed by the pouro authority. The following table shows waste disposal system in this area.

Table 3.11 – Statistics on waste disposal & management system until 2012 (modified)

ID	Description	Number, area, amount etc	
1	Number of garbage truck	1.5 ton	1
		3.0 ton	1
		5.0 ton	-
2	Number of dustbin	17	

ID	Description	Number, area, amount etc
3	Number of transfer station	-
4	Area of solid waste disposal ground	0.10 acre
5	Total production of garbage	12.65 ton (every day)
6	Total collection of garbage	10.50 ton (every day)
7	Door to door waste collection	No
8	Number of cleaner	69
9	Total cost in this sector in 2010-11 FY	2362574.00 tk.
10	Production of fertilizer from garbage & amount	No
11	Production of biogas from garbage & number of household using this	No

(Source: Information desk, Muktagachha pouroshova, 2014)

The pouro officials answered to the researcher that this survey was conducted in 2012. Since no survey was conducted, they could not tell the exact figure on waste disposal. However, they also said that there should not be much difference between the present situation of waste disposal and in the year of 2012. The photograph on the following shows open space garbage disposal from residence. This causes environmental pollution.

Drainage & sewerage system

Drainage and sewerage are important to wash out waste materials from the residence and commercial areas. In this area drainage system is not good at all. The pouro authority tries to improve the condition. Most of the inhabitants say that drains are not cleaned properly and the workers are not conscious of this. The following table shows data on drainage & sewerage system, which were collected in 2012. The officials said that drains showed in the table in need to be repaired have already been repaired and also more workers have been employed for cleaning purposes.

Table 3.12 – Statistics on drainage & sewerage system until 2012 (modified)

ID	Type	Length (km)	Condition of Drainage system	
			Need to repair	No need to repair
1	Brick drain	17.167	14.167	3.00
2	RCC drain	12.44	-	12.44
3	Primary Khal/ drain	5.91	5.91	-
4	Katcha drain	23.51	23.51	-
Total		59.027	43.587	15.44

(Source: Information desk, Muktagachha pouroshova, 2014)

The photograph on the following shows the quality of drainage system in this area. The common feature here is that drains are unclean and uncovered.

Literacy & educational institutions

As we all know, education is the backbone of a nation. Without education no nation can develop and go forward. In our country literacy rate is not so good. However, the recent government is trying hard to improve literacy rate. According to Banglapedia report on Muktagachha, literacy and educational information is the following: average literacy - 35.3% (male - 38.4%, female 32.2%); educational institutions: college-10, secondary school - 42, primary school - 144, regional scout training centre - 1, regional cooperative institute - 1, madrasa - 52. The noted educational institutions are: Ram Kishore High School (1300), Nagendra Narayan Primary School (1907), Kheruajani High School (1899) and MN Pilot Girls' High School (1907).

Parents of the children in this area are much more anxious about the study. At present, competition in schools is getting high. Nowadays, one can see every day morning picture of students going to private tutor houses or coaching centers. The two photographs on the following indicate that a mentally disabled school is located in this town. There is only one type of this school here. There are thousands of disabled children in this area. Most of the families are poor and lead miserable life. In order to educate disabled children, a disabled school called "Shopno Kuri" was established here in 2011. It is the only school for disabled children. The school started its work with 400 students. It is located in Aatani bazaar road of this town. Teachers work hard to educate them. Besides education, vocational training is given to students here to develop their livelihood. Parents of one mentally disabled child told the researcher: *"My child is mentally disabled. Before the establishment of this school I really felt bad when I saw children going to school with bags on their shoulders except my child. However, after the establishment of this school, all parents of disabled children and me too are happy. My child learnt many things and he can express his emotions, which I could not do alone. I am really grateful to Shopno Kuri School and teachers of this school."* The following table shows information about educational institutions in this area. The pouro authority said that present conditions of these educational institutions are good. There is no university here. Students are seen going to Dhaka, Mymensingh Sadar or other parts of the country to get higher education. There is one public library guided by the pouroshova. However, at present some public libraries are established with personal assistance. This helps to enhance education, as well as general knowledge of people.

Table 3.13 – Information about educational institutions until 2012 (modified)

ID	Description	Number/amount	Present condition
1	Primary school guided by pourashova	--	--
2	High school guided by pourashova	--	--
3	College/university guided by pourashova	--	--
4	Total primary school (govt-non govt.)	12	Good
5	Total high school (govt.-non govt.)	05	Good
6	Number of school & college	10	Good
7	Number of college	05	Good
8	Number of university	--	--
9	Number of medical college	--	--
10	Number of Madrasha	02	Good
11	Kawmi Madrasha	05	Medium
12	Number of library	01	Good
13	Number of disabled school	01	Good

(Source: Information desk, Muktagachha pouroshova, 2014)

Road & communication facilities

The town is well connected by a road network. However, most of the streets are narrow and driving a car is difficult. The highway that runs across Muktagachha town connects the main town of Muktagachha with the northern and eastern parts of Bangladesh. Muktagachha is called the gateway of Mymensingh District. Roads of the city are owned and maintained by the Pourashava. The pouro authority tries hard to improve the quality of roads. However, the condition of feeder roads is not so good.. For intra connection to the town people use CNG vehicle with two - stroke engine, rickshaw, van, etc. Van is popularly used in rural areas, but it is also used in town areas because of its low costs. The link with Dhaka was established around 1865 with the laying of railway lines. At that time people had to go to Mymensingh town in order to go to Dhaka. The road link went via Tangail until 1979 when President Ziaur Rahman instructed that the half-finished new highway between Dhaka and Mymensingh via Bhaluka be opened. The distance from Dhaka to Mymensingh is about 120 km (75 mi) north from the Mohakhali bus stop. Nowadays, journey by bus is very comfortable because of some good quality bus services. Muktagachha has its own bus service connected to Dhaka. Generally, it is about 2.30 to 3 hour journey from Dhaka to Muktagachha, though it may take little more time depending upon traffic jams and other conditions of the road. The Dhaka-Mymensingh highway is one of the busiest highways of the country. Moreover, due to recent land development there has been an increase in traffic. The pavement conditions have improved in recent years. During June-July, which is the season of jackfruit ripening, the overall travel time may be longer because of vendors selling jackfruit in Mauna, Seed Store, and Bhaluka. The bus fare always changes depending upon the fuel price. According to Banglapedia report, there is 100 km pucca road, 11 km semi-pucca road and 742.15 km mud road. The table on the following presents statistics on road conducted by the pouro authority. The table indicates that there is the total of 35.50 km of carpeting road, but it is not in a good condition. Katcha road is 40.68 km and it is in medium and bad condition.

Table 3.14 – Statistics on road condition until 2012 (modified)

ID	Type	Length (km)	Condition of roads (length of road)		
			good	medium	bad
1	Carpeting	35.50	-	20.00	15.50
2	H.B.B	1.25	-	-	1.25
3	Soling	-	-	-	-
4	CC/RCC	7.00	-	4.00	3.00
5	WBM	0.50	-	-	0.50
6	Katcha	40.68	-	13.60	27.08
7	Others		-	-	-
Total		84.93	-	37.60	47.33

(Source: Information desk, Muktagachha pouroshova, 2014)

The following table shows the number of bridges and culvert. The total number of bridges here is 33 including 22, which should be repaired. Furthermore, there are 64 culverts including 34, which should be repaired.

Table 3.15 – *Statistics on bridge and culvert until 2012 (modified)*

ID	Description	Number	Length (km)	No need to repair
1	Number of bridges	33	150	22
2	Number of culvert	64	80	34
	Total	97	230	56

(Source: Source: Information desk, Muktagachha pouroshova, 2014)

Gas facilities

Muktagachha town was connected to national gas distribution network in 2005. However, most people still use kerosene stove or firewood oven. Also, many kitchens run on liquefied petroleum gas available in steel bottles.

Newspapers & periodicals

Besides national dailies there is a good circulation of local newspapers and periodicals. They are weekly- Aloran Barta, fortnightly - Sabar Katha and periodical - Sonali Sis. The defunct ones are Promodi, Surid, Nirmallah, Desher Khabar, Muktakantha and Ajker Muktagachha.

Internet facilities

At present, the importance of the Internet cannot be ignored. The main advantage of the Internet is that it has made information available in a quick and easy manner, publicly accessible and within easy reach. It has revolutionized communications and social networking, creating the zone, which was so international that a new law had to be introduced to govern it.

People communicate, share data and work on the Internet all day, every day, without realizing that it is completely decentralized. The Internet plays a great role in removing the borders between nations, and it assists in the process of globalization. In a matter of seconds we can communicate with people around the world, whether for important business matters or just talking to friends. The Internet service in this upazilla is a recent phenomenon. People in this area do not exactly know when the Internet service started in this area. However, in 2003 GP Internet service was initiated here. BTCL started its journey in 2007. At present, many cyber centers are seen here. They offer computer training programs, network browsing and other computer training programs.

Post office

The upazilla post office is located near Muktagachha thana. Most of the respondents said that it was established a long time ago. However, nobody including the officials in this sector could name the exact year of its establishment. Some say that it was estab-

lished on 1st April 1933 whereas some others say that it was established on 1st May. The postal code of Muktagachha is 2210. Since this is the age of modern technology and nowadays most of the communication is performed through the Internet, mobile phone and other devices, the activities of post office have been slowed down. Yet, every day lots of official letters, foreign activities and postal orders are performed through this.

Market & bazaar facilities

There are 18 hats and bazaars, and 5 fairs. The most noted ones are Dorichari Ani Bazar, Raghunathpur (Rouarchar) Hat, Chechua Hat, Gabtali Hat, Dropour Hat, Kutubpur Shivaratri Mela, Ramchandrapur Mela, Lakshmikhola Mela, Sapanna Prahar Mela.

Entertainment facilities

Entertainment facilities here are not sufficient. There is playground, cinema hall, udan, auditorium and jamindar bari here. However, the facilities are very poor.

Land utilization and town planning

Since in Muktagachha town urbanization process is gradually developed, town planning is very important. Therefore, the pouro authority made statistical report of land utilization of this area. The following table shows that the land of Muktagachha is utilized for residential, commercial, road and communication, wetlands, entertainment, institution, industry, agriculture, open space and other purposes. The rate of utilization is also indicated here. The conclusion from the table is that the land is mostly used for residential purposes. Having in mind rapid urbanization trend here the pouro authority requests people to build their houses and other infrastructure in a planned way.

Table 3.16 – Land utilization and town planning data of the total land of 1747.46 ha

ID	Description	Amount (hector)	Rate of use (%)
1	Residential	561.63	32.14
2	Commercial	12.98	0.74
3	Road/communication	38.39	2.02
4	Wetlands	186.85	10.69
5	Entertainment	1.09	0.06
6	Institute	12.51	0.72
7	Industry	7.38	0.42
8	Agricultural area	635.39	36.36
9	Open space	279.54	16.00
10	Others	11.70	0.85

(Source: Information desk, Muktagachha pouroshova, 2014)

Urban problems and its solution in Muktagachha town

As we all know, urbanization is the inevitable destiny of the human civilization. However, in developing countries the process of urbanization faces many problems. Most of the time proper urbanization planning is not seen. Bangladesh is not exception to this situation. Mismanagement is present here from divisional sector to the local union porishad sector. In this section an analysis of the urban services and problems that the people of Muktagachha face will be discussed.

Analysis from the findings

From the field survey and after analyzing urban services that people of Muktagachha get, it has been found that 82% of the respondents answered that they faced many problems in getting urban services and 18% of the respondents said that they did not face many problems. They also said that although they did not face many problems still they experienced some problems to get some services.

Table 4.1 – Problems in getting urban services

ID	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	82	82%
No	18	18%
Total	100	100%

(Source: Field survey, 2014)

Most of the respondents (72%) said that they faced a great problem in getting electricity facility. They said that it took long time to get connection. Also, load shedding is a major factor of this problem. Then drainage & sewerage system comes. 14% of the respondents said that they faced problems because of poor drainage & sewerage management system. 8% said that road and communication system was not good enough. 3% said that they did not get proper health facilities. Only 1% of people said that water crisis is their main problem. However, it is well understood that electricity problem is the main problem here.

Graph 4.1 – Highest problematic urban service sectors
(Source: Field survey, 2014)

Status of electricity supply

As we have already learned, people of this area are supplied with electricity by the Rural Electrification Committee and the director said that electricity fall is coming down to zero. However, the respondents said different things. They said that load shedding is like a perpetual event in their life. Most of them said that every morning from 6.30-7.30 am load shedding occurs. It also occurs in the evening lasting from 30 minutes to an hour. One of the respondents said: *“If there is no load shedding a whole day then we think what’s going on today! Do the officials forget about electricity out?”* However, the secretary of the Rural Electrification Committee said that they would not stop the supply. Only if there is an unexpected situation like blasting of transformer, repairing of electric line, giving new connection during various natural disasters (storm, flood, cyclone, etc.) they are forced to stop supply of electricity to protect the whole system from being destructed (Cvetković, 2016ab; Cvetković & Gačić, 2016; Cvetković, Gačić & Jakovljević, 2016; Cvetković, 2017; Cvetković, Gačić & Babić, 2017; Cvetković, Lipovac & Milojković, 2016). From the analysis it has been found that there is a difference between summer and winter load shedding type. Since these two seasons are more specific than other seasons in Bangladesh the researcher put emphasis on these two seasons. Load shedding in summer is more frequent than in winter. In our country, generally, summer season starts from the month of April and it lasts until August, sometimes until September, too. The following graph shows the highest seasonal frequency of load shedding in this area. The graph says that 90% of the respondents answered there is the highest frequency of load shedding from April-June. Some of them said that at this time electricity went out at least 5-6 times within 30 minutes - 1 hour duration. Later we can see that from July to September the rate of load shedding is 5%, 3% from October to December and 2% from January to March. The lowest frequency of load shedding is from January to March due to winter season. At this time the demand for electricity is not great in amount anymore. Therefore, the authority supplies electricity to people in their desired amount. Yet, load shedding has not entirely vanished!

Graph 4.2 – Highest seasonal frequency of load shedding
(Source: Field survey, 2014)

Status of load shedding in summer Season

From the following graph it can be seen that load shedding occurs more in summer season. Most of the respondents (79%) answered that load shedding occurs 3-4 times in this season. 16% of the respondents said that it happens more than 5 times a day! 3% and 2% of the respondents answered that load shedding occurs 2-3 times and 1-2 times respectively.

Graph 4.3 – Status of load shedding in summer in Muktagachha town
(Source: Field survey, 2014)

Some of the respondents found out why load shedding is greatly present in this season. They said that when there is greater demand for electricity more load shedding occurs. They suggested the following reasons: it is summer season and it is much hotter, so people need more electricity to run cooling instruments (fans, refrigerators, air conditioners, etc.). That is why the demand for electricity is greater and more load shedding is necessary; this is the time for paddy cultivation, so the need for irrigation is more present at this time. Irrigation needs more electricity. The authority needs to supply electricity for irrigation. Most of the respondents said that “Every night in summer season, generally from 10-11 p.m. load shedding occurs in residential areas and it lasts at least 2-3 hours or sometimes until bazaar times!”; in summer season storm surges and raining are more frequent phenomena. Therefore, at this time officials of the Rural Electrification Committee stop electricity supply in order to prevent the destruction of supply lines, accidents, etc. Sometimes load shedding lasts from 1 day to several days depending on situation. Some people said that there were major storm surges in this area a year ago, which destroyed many transformers and electricity lines and load shedding lasted for 4 days. This created many problems to people’s life and business, as well.

Status of load shedding in winter season

Load shedding in winter season is not absent here, although the demand for electricity is not so great anymore. 72% of the respondents answered that load shedding occurs 2-3 times a day and it lasts for ½ - 2 hours a day. The other 19% and 9% of the respondents replied that it occurs 3-4 times and 1-2 times a day respectively. More than five times load shedding occurrence is not seen here as replied by the respondents.

Graph 4.4 – Status of load shedding in winter in Muktagachha town
(Source: Field survey, 2014)

Problems in electricity supply

Here are some problems identified by the respondents, which they face in getting electricity supply: electricity bill is much higher than they expected; officials are not conscious of the need to repair electricity lines; frequent load shedding occurs here; electric poles are adjacent to houses, trees and other objects. This may cause accidents if there is any leakage of electric wires; the number of lamp posts is less than the demand and most of the lamp posts do not work. However, the lamp post data from pourashava urges that there is a sufficient amount of lamp posts and it covers several areas.

Table 4.2 – Lamp post data

ID	Description	km	Number
1	Number of lamp post & length of road	47.30	860
		51%	
2	Coverage of lamp post (%)	48.40%	

(Source: Information desk, Muktagachha pourashova, 2014)

There are some measures proposed by the respondents that have to be considered to minimize problems of electricity supply. These are: metering and monitoring the use of units. A digital electric meter can help for this; monitoring is necessary to identify leakage of electric wires; people should be aware of using electricity. They should not keep putting on electric materials unnecessarily; people should pay electricity bill timely; everyone should be careful while handling electric instruments to avoid unexpected accidents. Since we already know that inhabitants of this upazilla get electricity from Mymensingh Rural Electrification Committee, if problems occur during transfer of electricity from the national grid to this Committee, then inhabitants face problems like load shedding, too. The photographs on the following indicate location of Mymensingh Rural Electrification Committee-1. It also works as the head office. It provides services to 8 upazillas of Mymensingh (Mymensingh Sadar Upazilla (partially), Muktagachha and Phulbaria) and Tangail (Modhupur, Dhonbari, Gopalpur, Ghatail and Bhuapur) District. We already know this from the previous chapter.

Present status of water supply

There is a variety of sources of water in this area. People get water from tube well, personal motor, supply water and other sources (from other people's houses). The following graph shows that 69% of the interviewees answered that they get water from personal motor, 19% of people get water from tube well, 9% gets water from supply and 3% from other sources.)

Graph 4.5 – Sources of water supply
(Source: Field survey, 2014)

It has become clear that the frequency of getting water from personal motor is greater than from other sources. The reason behind this is the fact that people can get water in any amount by a switch on their motor. It is very hard work to get water from tube wells. It makes people tired. Particularly in winter seasons (December-January) it is difficult to get water because water levels go out of the reach. Therefore, at this time people add

extra pipes to the existing tube wells to reach water level. In rainy season water comes to the reach, so at this time they withdraw extra pipes from tube wells. This system is costly and tiresome because this process has to be done every year, that is supply water has to be stored. This work is very tiring to most people. It ensures 100% pure water. It helps to fulfill urgent huge water demand. It reduces uncertainty of supply water. People, who use supply water say that this water fulfills their water demand more or less. However, sometimes they face problems when they have some occasions like wedding or others because in this case they need more water and they cannot get sufficient water. Moreover, when a major disaster occurs and electricity is blown out this creates a problem in getting water. However, the overall water demand of people is fulfilled by this source according to answers of most people. People get water 3 times a day in morning (2 hours), at noon (2 hours) and at night (3 hours). They have to store water. The table on the following shows time and duration of water supply by the pouro authority.

Table 4.3 – Time & duration of water supply

ID	Time	Duration
Morning	6-8 am	2 hours
Noon	12-2 pm	2 hours
Night	5-7.30 pm	3 hours

(Source: Field survey, 2014)

There is difference between monthly payment of residential and commercial water supply. It also depends on diameter of the connection. Statistics on residential water supply conducted by the pouroshova (Table 4.3) indicates that the pouro authority can make the total of 737 connections to its inhabitants including 76 connections that are 13mm (0.5 inches) and they have to pay 75 tk. monthly. There are 651 connections (maximum), which are 19mm (0.75 inches) and they have to pay 110 tk. Furthermore, there are 10 connections, which are 25 mm (1 inch) and they have to pay 200 tk. per month. This statistics was made in 2012. Therefore, the officials say that there may be some changes in the data, but they also say that a tendency to use personal motor is rapidly increasing in this area and sometimes people cut down water supply connections.

Table 4.4 – Total number of residential connection & monthly payment

ID	Diameter of connection	Number of connection	Monthly payment (tk)/thousands
1	13 mm (0.5 inches)	76	75.00
2	19 mm (0.75 inches)	651	110.00
3	25 mm (1 inch)	10	200.00
Total 737			

(Source: Information desk, Muktagachha pouroshova, 2014)

The following table shows that commercial water users have to pay more than residential ones. Commercial water users get more water unlike residential water users. The table indicates that until 2012 the total number of commercial connections was 12. There are 8

connections, which are 13mm (0.5 inches) and they have to pay 250 tk. monthly. Also, there are 2 connections, which are 19mm (0.75 inches) and they have to pay 450 tk. a month. Also, there are 2 connections, which are 25 mm (1 inch) and they have to pay 750 tk. per month. Actually, at present most of the commercial users have personal motor.

Table 4.5 – Total number of commercial connection & monthly payment

Id	Diameter of connection	Number of connection	Monthly payment (tk)/thousands
1	13 mm (0.5 inches)	8	250.00
2	19 mm (0.75 inches)	2	450.00
3	25 mm (1 inch)	2	750.00
Total 12			

(Source: Information desk, Muktagachha pouroshova, 2014)

The following map shows the location of water supply pump. These are marked by W1, W2 and W3. W1 represents water supply pump 1. It is located in the pouroshova compound. The foundation stone of this water supply was installed on 8th March 1995. Due to the increasing number of people and huge demand for water the pouro authority installed other two water supply pumps. W2 or water supply pump 2 is located on Moddhohishha road of Muktagachha municipal area. It was installed on 22nd April 1996. W3 represents water supply pump 3. It is the last water supply pump constructed by the pouro authority. The foundation stone of this pump was installed on 9th December 2011. At present, these three pumps can mostly fulfill water demand of people.

Map 4.1 – Location of water supply pump
(Source: Muktagachha pouroshova.org)

Status of waste disposal

As we have already found out from the previous chapter, the pouro authority claimed that their workers work conscientiously to collect waste materials and try to make environment clean. There are garbage trucks, which collect waste from dustbins. There is the waste disposal ground here and a garbage truck that disposes waste to this area. There is no waste treatment plant here. The respondents said that medical and industrial waste is also disposed in open space. This poses a threat to the environment and it also creates health hazards.

Graph 4.6 – Present situation of waste disposal by pouro authority
(Source: Field survey, 2014)

This table presents waste disposal information. 62% of interviewees said that they throw waste materials to vacant areas. A researcher asked them why they do this. One of the respondents answered that “sometimes dustbins are far from house and sometimes dustbins become too messy to go there and throw waste there. So, we throw waste to vacant areas close to our house. We know that this causes environmental degradation. We will do our best not to dispose waste to vacant areas”. This table also shows that 12% of people dispose their waste to road sides. This is also a harmful method. 3% of people throw waste to their home yard. Only 23% of people throw waste to dustbins.

Table 4.6 – Waste Disposal System

ID	Frequency	Percentage
Home Yard	3	3%
Beside the Road	12	12%
Dustbin	23	23%
Vacant Area	62	62%
Waste collected by pouro Authority	0	0%
Others	0	0%
Total	100	100%

(Source: Field survey, 2014)

Interviewees suggested the following measures to improve waste disposal: waste should be thrown to dustbins, not in open space nor beside the road; garbage treatment plant should be initiated; workers and cleaners have to work sincerely when cleaning dustbins; people have to be conscious of the importance of healthy environment; garbage disposal ground should be made available.

Status of drainage & sewerage system

On the one hand, neat and clean drainage and sewerage system ensures good and healthy life. On the other hand, filthy and messy drainage system threatens life. The majority of the developed countries have very good drainage system and citizens lead healthy life and have more urban facilities. Our country is a developing country. Most development activities are not performed in a planned way here. 55% of people here said that the present condition of drainage and sewerage system is bad. Inhabitants face a lot of problems because of poor drainage system. Interviewees have found out some causes of poor drainage sewerage system. They are the following: drains are not cleaned properly and timely; cleaners do not carefully clean drains; sometimes people throw household waste to drains and this blocks the normal flow of water in drains; most drains are in a poor condition and broken in several places. Dirty water overflows the roads; sometimes cleaners pile waste products beside drains after cleaning them. In the rainy season rain water washes this waste to drains and fills up drains. Also, filthy water overflows the surroundings. To overcome this problem the following steps should be taken: drains have to be cleaned timely and properly; cleaners should be sincere; people have to get an idea about bad effects of throwing away waste into drains. This hampers the natural flow of water in drains; broken and old drains have to be repaired.

Graph 4.7 – Scenario of drainage & sewerage system
(Source: Field survey, 2014)

Problems in getting health facilities

It is well known that good brings happiness. In Muktagachha town, people get health services from upazilla health complex, as well as private hospitals. 68% of people said that health facilities are in a moderate condition. 25% said they are in a good condition and 7% that they are in a bad condition. None of the respondents answered that they are in a very bad condition. The following graph indicates the present situation of health facilities in this area.

Graph 4.8 – Present situation of health facilities

(Source: Field survey, 2014)

The following table shows travelling distances of health centers from residence. 69% of respondents said that they have health centers in less than 1 km travelling distance. This shows that the availability of health facilities is good. 15% said health centers are located within 1-2 km distance, 12% and 4% of respondents replied they have health centers that are 3-4 km away and more than 4 km away. However, the overall distances are not so long from most of the residences.

Table 4.7 – Distance of nearest health centers

ID	Frequency	Percentage
<1 km	69	69%
1-2 km	15	15%
3-4 km	12	12%
>4 km	4	4%
Total	100	100%

(Source: Field survey, 2014)

Although health centers are not far, people still face some problems in getting health services. Some of the problems of upazilla health complex are discussed below: there are not sufficient ambulances to fulfill emergency needs. Due to unavailability of ambulances, poor people sometimes carry their patients by rickshaws or vans; there is no sufficient amount of oxygen cylinders in upazilla health complex; there are not enough beds; most of the respondents answered that behavior of the officials and workers in upazilla health complex is not good enough. The researcher has also experienced this situation. Surgery room

is not neat and clean; officials are not careful to patients. It could be seen that they use the same syringes. This is very harmful to patients' bodies; poor people do not get medicines that are supposed to be given by the hospital authority because the authority sold medicines to dispensaries. Most of the nurses are not experienced enough. There are other problems of upazilla health complex and in private clinics. The most important problem is that there are not experienced doctors. Also, nurses are not fully educated and experienced. To overcome the existing problems the following measures should be taken as proposed by interviewees: the number of ambulances should be increased, as well as the number of oxygen cylinders. It should be made sure that each person can get an oxygen cylinder at any time when it is necessary; the quality of health facilities has to be improved, as well as behavior of the officials; number of employees should increase and they have to be experienced; the number of beds has to increase; there should be a good quality of medicines; hospital compound should be clean and pollution free.

Present status of road & communication facilities

Good roads and transportation are very important for communication between places. The results obtained from the survey data show that 53% of the interviewees said that the present situation of roads is bad. 33% said it is moderate. 8% and 6% of the respondents said that the condition of roads is very bad and good respectively. The respondents found out some causes of poor road conditions. They are: roads are broken and holes are present in most parts of roads; poor ingredients are used in road construction, and carpeting of roads is done properly; in rainy season there is water on roads, which damages them ; the pouro authority is not aware of the need to maintain roads; roads are narrow and congested; there are lots of vehicles on roads (bus, truck, car, rickshaw, van, CNG, etc.), which causes traffic jam; the condition of feeder roads is even worse; most of the time there is traffic jam on bus stands and it wastes valuable time; the number of speed breakers is great and it causes accidents most of the time. Due to breaking the speed in June 2014 a primary school boy got killed while passing the road at Chhatrashia bazaar road in Muktagachha; there are not enough street lamps and some street lamps are not working at all. This also influences the occurrence of accidents.

Graph 4.9 – Quality of roads & communication system (Source: Field survey, 2014)

Photographs on the following show the existing road conditions. Photographs 1 and 2 indicate miserable road conditions. These are covered with brick and with no carpeting. Photographs 3 & 4 also show the same condition of roads. Photograph 5 is the everyday picture of Muktagachha bus station. This area is always overcrowded and congested and it threatens to have accidents. Graph on the following shows the highest seasonal frequency of worse road and communication system. 85% and 12% of the respondents said that roads become worse in the pre-monsoon and during monsoon period.

Graph 4.10 – Seasonality of worse road & communication system
(Source: Field survey, 2014)

The interviewees proposed some steps that should be taken to improve road facilities. They are: to use high-quality ingredients for constructing roads; roads should be maintained properly and the pouro authority should be careful; vehicles such as rickshaws, vans, cycles should not be allowed to the highway; roads should be repaired immediately when problems occur; the number of street lamps should be increased; people should be aware while crossing busy roads.

Gas facilities and their problems

We have already found out that Muktagachha got connected to the national gas distribution network on 3rd October 2005. However, the majority of poor people still uses kerosene stove or firewood oven. Some people use liquefied petroleum gas. The majority of liquefied petroleum gas users said that they had applied for gas connection at gas supply office. The following table shows that according to 81% of the respondents gas facilities are available in this area. 19% said that this service is not available to them.

Table 4.8 – Availability of Fuel Gas Facilities

ID	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	81	81%
No	19	19%
Total	100	100%

(Source: Field survey, 2014)

There are some problems in getting gas facilities. They are: it takes long time to get connection; people have to pay more money to get connection for the first time; there is huge corruption in this sector. According to the interviewees, the following measures can be taken to control problems in gas facilities: there should be awareness of usefulness of gas facilities and damages occur due to careless use; people should be careful when using gas; gas stove should not keep burning unnecessarily; wet clothes should not be dried using gas stove.

Prospects of mosquito killing program

Mosquitoes are generally considered annoying and they may also transmit diseases, thus leading to a variety of human efforts to eradicate or reduce their presence. It bothers people around homes, in parks or recreational areas. Prospects of mosquito killing program are not good in this area. 96% of the interviewees said that no steps are taken by the pouro authority to kill mosquitoes. 4% of people said some measures are taken to control mosquitoes like cutting down brushwood, spreading medicines, cleaning drains, etc., but these measures are taken only one or two times a year. Most of the time people have to do this work on their own.

Table 4.9 – Mosquito killing programme by pouro authority

ID	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	4	4%
No	96	96%
Total	100	100%

(Source: Field survey, 2014)

Entertainment facilities and their present situation

Entertainment is a very essential element of leading sound and good life. Entertainment facilities in this upazilla are not in a good condition. There are 2 playgrounds, but the present condition of these playgrounds is not so good. There is no shishu park here. There are 4 auditoriums here, but they are in a moderate condition. There are 6 cinema halls, but the majority of the audience is illiterate and the environment of this area is not good. The most remarkable place of Muktagachha is the relics of jamindar bari. Muktagachha jamindar bari is decrepit. At present, due to its appeal as a tourist attraction, the pouro authority has taken repairing program.

Table 4.10 – *Information about entertainment facilities (modified)*

ID	Description	Number/ amount	Present condition
1	Playground	2	Medium
2	Shishu park	--	
3	Other parks	1	
4	Auditorium	4	Medium
5	Cinema hall/theater	6	
6	Gym	--	
7	Museum	--	
8	Fair place	--	
9	Remarkable place	2	Decrepit

(Source: Information desk, Muktagachha pouroshova, 2014)

The following figures show that 80% of the interviewees said that entertainment facilities are not sufficient to them. 20% said that facilities are more or less sufficient.

Table 4.11 – *Entertainment Facilities*

ID	Frequency	Percentage
Sufficient	20	20%
Insufficient	80	80%
Total	100	100%

(Source: Field survey, 2014)

Problems in slum areas

Slums areas are also seen here. Generally, these areas are occupied by poor groups of people. The statistics was collected on slum areas by the pouro authority. They have found out the following characteristics of slums in this area: 50% of households live in katcha and unstable houses; 50% of households are unskilled or poorly skilled in main occupation; densely populated/chaos areas (300 households living in 1 acre area); basic services are insufficient or absent; monthly income per head is 700 tk. or less; houses look alike and are close to each other. The pouroshova and various non - governmental organizations work to improve the quality of life of the poor slum people and give training to them to make them self-sustainable. The following table indicates the location, area and number of households in these slum areas. It has been seen that Reshi para slum has larger area than other slums and it is also inhabited by more people.

Table 4.12 – *Statistics on slum areas*

ID	Name of slum area	Area (acre)	Number of household
1	Refozi potty	.13	20
2	Pill khana	.81	60
3	Shaba polly	.80	50
4	Reshi para	4.00	100
5	Laxmikhola (near pouro grave yard)	.40	90
6	Sandar potty (Nandibari)	.35	45
7	Payerkandi (porba para)	.50	35

(Source: Information desk, Muktagachha pouroshova)

Overall findings

On the basis of the discussion on urban services of Muktagachha town, the following overall findings can be drawn: there are problems in electricity supply; load shedding is the main problem. Mymensingh Rural Electrification Board is trying to solve this problem; most people have personal motor to meet their water demand and it ensures maximum pure water supply. It is tiresome work to get water from manual tube wells. There is the uncertainty of water supply by the pouro authority if there is load shedding for couple of days. Water supply does not ensure maximum pure water supply; health centers are not far from the residence. Besides upazilla health complex, a lot of private hospitals have been established. Poor village dwellers come more to upazilla health complex to get health services; people throw waste in dustbins, open spaces, beside the roads and their home yard. The frequency of throwing waste to open space and beside roads is higher. This increases environmental pollution; drains are not in a good condition. They are mostly overflowing. Drains have to be repaired; the present condition of educational system is not bad at all. There is a school for disabled children. Gas supply in this area is sufficient, though people face problems to get connection for the first time. The quality of highway is good, but feeder roads are in a miserable condition. They have to be repaired. There is a good circulation of national, as well as local newspapers and periodicals. There is a public library in this area. It will help enhance knowledge of people and students. The Internet facilities are made available with the improved service including some wireless network systems such as Grameenphone, 3G teletalk, citycell zoom ultra-package, which are remarkable. Broad band connections are also available here. The activities of post office are now decreasing due to technological advancement. There is a number of hats and bazaars here. However, the environmental quality of these areas is not good. Most bazaars are situated beside the highway. It causes traffic jam. Entertainment facilities are not sufficient in number. Some initiatives have been taken by governmental organizations and private sectors to improve entertainment facilities.

Conclusion

Having in mind everything discussed, it can be said that Bangladesh is one of the world's most densely populated country. Furthermore, it has faced rapid population growth throughout the last century, although the population growth rate has somewhat decreased to a moderate level in recent times. At present, the expansion of urban population and urban construction have been so alarming that urban safety has become the crucial issue in Bangladesh. According to the recent UN data, approximately 25 percent of Bangladesh population currently lives in urban areas. Although it is the small and not well - developed urban center, Muktagachha has also become overcrowded and the quality of urban facilities there is also deteriorating. Due to this, normal functioning of people is interrupted. Therefore, these problems should have special consideration at policy and program making level. The problems have to be eliminated by the collective approach of the Government, as well as non-governmental initiatives, where the need and expectation of people

will get maximum priority. There should be proper planning by the pouro authority and the officials should be conscious of their duty. Social workers as the intellectuals of these sectors can play a vital role here by taking humanitarian issues first.

Recommendation

After evaluating all of the findings in this study, the following general recommendations can be made: electricity supply should be provided to all inhabitants of this area without any disturbance, and illegal connection should be strictly handled; water supply system should be improved, and the good quality of water guaranteed to all inhabitants; health services at upazilla health complex should be improved. Experienced doctors and nurses should be employed. Private hospitals should be given approval by the pouro authority after proper evaluation. There should be enough dustbins for waste disposal. Dustbins should be cleaned properly. People have to be aware of not throwing waste in open spaces. There should be garbage disposal treatment plant. The quality of drainage and sewerage system should be improved. Old and broken drains should be repaired. People should be encouraged to use toilets, which have septic tank and not to use open spaces. The quality of education has to improve. The number of public libraries should increase, as well as a circulation of books, newspapers, journals, periodicals, etc. There should be ensured easy accessible to all classes of people to meet their queries; An evening school for the old illiterate people can be established to enhance literacy rate. A damaged road should be repaired as soon as possible. Before the beginning of monsoon period roads should be repaired. Drivers should be careful while driving. Also, people should be careful when crossing a busy road. It will reduce the rate of accidents. People should be careful when using gas. Gas stove should not keep burning unnecessarily. Clothes should not dry by using gas stove. People should ensure easy access to the Internet service. For this purpose several WiFi hotspots should be established. The environment of market and bazaar should be enhanced. Entertainment facilities have to be enhanced. More parks are needed. The present decrepit condition of Muktagachha Jamindar bari has to be changed. The pouro authority should make effective planning to improve facilities of urban services. People should be aware of proper utilization of urban services.

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